

DEVELOPMENT OF A PLANT COLLECTION WITH HEPATOPROTECTIVE ACTIVITY

Tursunova S.T.

Khalilova Sh.R.

Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute, Tashkent, Republic of Uzbekistan

e-mail.ru: xalilova.shaxnoza@mail.ru, phone: (+99894)657-57-88.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12593279>

Relevance. Currently, liver pathologies caused by viral and chemical agents are widespread. In order to protect liver cells from the damaging effects of various factors, hepatoprotective drugs are used. Depending on the chemical composition and origin, hepatoprotectors are divided into several groups: preparations containing essential phospholipids; amino acids or their derivatives; antioxidant vitamins and vitamin-like compounds; preparations of animal and vegetable origin. As part of the complex pathogenetic therapy of a number of diseases, including those associated with damage to hepatocytes, hepatoprotective agents based on medicinal plant raw materials are widely used [1-3]. Their advantage, along with a sufficiently high efficiency, is high safety, low toxicity and minimal manifestation of negative side effects even with prolonged systematic use.

In this regard, it seems relevant to develop new effective and safe hepatoprotective drugs of plant origin.

The purpose of this study is to create effective, import-substituting medicines of plant origin for the creation of hepatoprotective medicines, we have conducted research to identify and study promising medicinal plants of the domestic flora.

Methods and techniques. As a hepatoprotective agent, we have proposed a collection containing columns with corn stigmas (*Zea mays* L.), flowers of sand immortelle (*Helichrysum arenarium* L.) and grass of meadow clover (*Trifolium pratense* L.), used in folk medicine as agents with choleric, hypolipidemic, hypoglycemic, anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory, antioxidant, choleric, etc. action.

It is believed that from the variety of biologically active substances of various plants included in the collection, the body has ample opportunities by self-regulation to select the missing components for it and include them in the metabolic processes.

The therapeutic effectiveness of the fees is due to the manifestation of general patterns of synergism of active and concomitant substances, summation and potentiation of their pharmacological effects, allowing to simultaneously solve several tasks with minimal risk of toxic and allergic complications.

Taking into account the "golden rule" of phytotherapy to give preference to plants growing in the climatic zone of the patient's residence, it seems advisable to include in the collections local medicinal plants approved for medical use from among the species that have proven themselves well in folk medicine and in the experiment in the treatment of the liver.

Results. As a result of the research, it can be concluded that the use of medicinal plants in the treatment of the liver has good clinical prospects. The use of the phytotherapy method undoubtedly increases the effectiveness of treatment and prevention of the liver, reduces the drug load.

Conclusions. Based on the analysis of data on the chemical composition of these plants and their application in folk medicine, it was assumed that a collection composed of corn stigmas,

sand immortelle flowers and meadow clover grass in a ratio of 1:1:1 (in weight parts) would have hepatoprotective properties.

List of used literature:

1. Morozov S.Yu. Hepatoprotectors in the practice of a clinician. Russian medical journal No. 1. pp.25-28.
2. Weiss R.F., Fintelmann F. Herbal medicine. Manual. M. 2004. pp.108, 274-275.
3. Bunatyan N.D., Gerasimova O.A., Sakharova T.S., Yakovleva L.V. Natural antioxidants as hepatoprotectors. Expert and wedge. pharmacol. 1999. No.2. pp.64-68.